

BRUCE: Bundle Recommendation Using Contextualized item Embeddings

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RecSys '22

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188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science (2022W)

Summary of Paper

- **Task:** Bundle recommendation
 - **Methodology:** Deep Neural Network (Transformer) – “BRUCE”
 - **Evaluation:** comparison to 4 baselines on 3 datasets
 - **Conclusion:** statistically significant improvement on all datasets
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Strategy for Reproducing Results

1. Read and analyze the paper
2. Check for discrepancies between paper and code
3. Run code on all 3 datasets (estimate of computation time, comparison to reported results)
4. Check if conclusions hold with different dataset splits

Intermediate Results

Faced Difficulties

- Code of **BRUCE** crashed when running it as described – fixed it
- Training computationally expensive (or even infeasible) with a single GPU
- No implementation for 1 baseline available

Evaluation of Experimental Setup & Key Findings

- Loss function for 1 dataset different (not documented in paper)
- No hyperparameter tuning for 2 baselines (TBC)
- Evaluation on test set runs immediately after training a *single configuration*
- Unclear how significance tests were performed

Steam dataset

	BPR			BRUCE		
	Reported	Reproduced	Diff. [%]	Reported	Reproduced	Diff. [%]
Recall@5	0.4254	0.4327	1.72	0.8799	0.8707	-1.05
MRR@5	0.3840	0.4239	10.39	0.7065	0.7024	-0.58
NDCG@5	0.3693	0.4028	9.07	0.7343	0.7298	-0.61

Youshu dataset

	BPR			BRUCE		
	Reported	Reproduced	Diff. [%]	Reported	Reproduced	Diff. [%]
Recall@5	0.0764	0.0766	0.26	0.1344	0.1282	-4.61
MRR@5	0.0942	0.0992	5.31	0.1465	0.1408	-3.89
NDCG@5	0.0638	0.0658	3.13	0.1068	0.1013	-5.14

NetEase dataset

computationally infeasible 🕒

Remaining Work

- Get at least 1 additional baseline up and running
- Focus on one dataset (**Steam**)
- Evaluate **Steam** with different splits (most probably 5-fold CV) on **BRUCE** + baselines
- Check if conclusions of paper still hold (significance testing)
- Summarize findings in report